

ENHANCING THE PROFESSIONAL AND CREATIVE COMPETENCES OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the development of professional and creative competence among future foreign language teachers based on modern pedagogical approaches. Professional and creative competence is determined not only by methodological skills but also by personal qualities such as independent thinking, adaptability, reflective approaches, creativity, and communicative activity. It is scientifically substantiated that the main didactic principles for developing professional and creative competence in language education are integrativeness, communicativeness and activity orientation. Furthermore, the study proposes approaches aimed at enhancing students' creative potential through the integrated development of methodological, digital, cultural, and reflective competencies. The research findings contribute to improving foreign language education processes and strengthening the professional and creative preparation of future teachers.*

Keywords: *professional and creative competence, foreign language education, CLIL, didactic principles, independent tasks, creativity, methodological approaches.*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization, one of the key factors ensuring the competitiveness of education is the preparation of modern, innovative, and creatively thinking educators. Enhancing the professional-creative competence of foreign language teachers not only increases students' motivation to learn languages but also determines their ability to think independently, engage in intercultural communication, and prepare for creative activities. In today's modern educational process, professional-creative competence is recognized as one of the essential competencies for foreign language teachers.

In the modern education system, the quality of education is significantly determined not only by teachers' theoretical knowledge but also by the level of development of their professional-creative competence. Particularly in the training of future foreign language teachers, creative approaches, innovative thinking, and the ability to work with modern technologies define their professional success. Therefore, forming and enhancing the professional-creative competence of future foreign language teachers has become one of the pressing directions in contemporary pedagogical research.

In today's globalized and competitive educational environment, the development of professional-creative competence for foreign language teachers is a critical issue. Advanced educational practices worldwide emphasize the formation of this competence. For instance, the education systems of Finland, Germany, and Japan have unique approaches that reflect both global trends and national characteristics.

The Finnish education system places high trust in teachers and strives to develop them as free, creative individuals. Teachers regularly participate in scientific-creative projects and conduct lessons based on interdisciplinary integrated approaches (e.g., CLIL, STEAM). Schools use methodological experiments and creative laboratories to refine teachers' pedagogical approaches. Teachers have the autonomy to independently shape and update their pedagogical practices. Through mentoring, reflective analysis, and professional development programs, their professional-creative activity is continuously supported.

In Germany, teachers' professional-creative activity is shaped through a robust theoretical-methodological foundation and practical training. Teachers undergo thorough preparation in pedagogical universities, acquiring skills in lesson design, innovative methodological approaches, and working with the CLIL principle. Regular seminars and didactic laboratories enhance their methodological thinking and creative activity. Additionally, teachers' involvement in updating educational content and developing methodological materials further boosts their professional activity.

In Japan, the education system prioritizes continuous teacher development and lesson analysis. The renowned "Lesson Study" method involves teachers observing, discussing, and refining each other's lessons. This process improves not only lesson quality but also teachers' professional-creative potential. Collective reflection, experience sharing, and designing lessons based on creative problem-solving encourage continuous learning. Alongside Japan's discipline-based pedagogy, these processes enhance teachers' internal motivation and innovative potential.

Overall, the experiences of these countries demonstrate that the following factors are crucial in forming the professional-creative activity of foreign language teachers:

- Encouraging personal initiative and independent exploration (Finland),
- Strong methodological and practical training (Germany),
- Collaborative and continuous improvement-based approaches (Japan).

These approaches can serve as effective models for developing the professional-creative potential of foreign language teachers. Therefore, studying and adapting advanced international experiences to the local context is a critical methodological task.

METHODOLOGY

The term *competence* (derived from the Latin *compeo*, meaning "I achieve, I am suitable, I correspond") refers to the set of knowledge, skills, and abilities an individual possesses. The concept of competence began to gain widespread use in the late 1960s and early 1970s. Competence represents the educational preparation required for a specialist to perform effectively in a specific field. It is a socially defined requirement, set by the state, for an individual's (worker's) educational or professional preparation to perform effectively in a given domain. Competence-based education enables learners to apply their acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities practically in their personal, professional, and social activities. Competence-based education fosters independence, active civic engagement, initiative, rational use of media resources and ICT, conscious career choices, healthy competition, and general cultural skills.

Professional and creative competence is determined not only by methodological skills but also by personal qualities. As L. Vygotsky (1991) emphasized, "Creativity is the ability of a person to apply their potential in new situations" (p. 101). Therefore, it is essential to develop independent thinking, adaptability, and a reflective approach in future teachers.

Enhancing professional and creative competence in the process of foreign language education primarily relies on the general laws and principles of didactics. In selecting educational content, integrativeness, communicativeness, and activity orientation play a key role. As N. I. Gez (2006) stated, "In the process of language learning, the learner must have the opportunity to develop creative thinking as a subject of activity" (p. 45). Thus, professional and creative competence is closely linked to learners' communicative activity.

Didactic tools and methods play a decisive role in developing creative competence. E. I. Passov (2010) emphasizes that the use of problematic situations and creative tasks in foreign language teaching leads to effective results.

Many renowned educators and methodological scholars around the world have conducted scientific research on this topic. They have examined issues related to professional and creative competence in the educational process and developed their own effective recommendations, proposals, models, and methods. Today, the results of their research are being applied in modern educational practices. In this article, sources from the world's leading academic databases and publishers were used to analyze the relevant literature.

I.A. Zimnyaya defines competence as a set of knowledge, skills, and abilities formed based on external demands, while competence is the level of readiness for real activity present in an individual. Subjectivity (subjectification) deepens this process through personal awareness and reflection.

V. Panfilova divides the professional-communicative competence of future teachers into eight sub-competencies: linguistic, discursive, oral speech, pragmatic, information-technological, strategic, sociocultural, and personal-creative. The personal-creative component is defined as the foundation of creative competence.

N. Almazova propose forming teachers' methodological creativity at the university level through a two-stage model: reproductive and reproductive-creative stages. They argue that lesson design, reflection, and independent methodological decision-making contribute to developing creative competence.

O. Byrdina demonstrate that professional-communicative competence can be developed through the CLIL methodology, fostering creative thinking, interdisciplinary approaches, and effective student communication.

Y. V. Borisova considers project work, debates, and tasks based on authentic materials effective for developing students' "soft skills" and language competencies. R.M. Horbatiuk proposes a project-based approach for developing professional vocabulary in "Business German" for energy engineering students.

M. Andrianova prove that creolized texts can prepare students for spontaneous oral speech, creative thinking, and intercultural communication. A. Shakiyeva recommend forming professional competence in distance learning conditions through a methodological system designed for platforms like Moodle, Zoom, Padlet, and Google Forms, which develop digital, communicative, and methodological competencies.

R. Sabirova propose a model for forming professional competence based on an integrative approach, combining personal growth, specialized skills, and self-development. M. Karimova and D. Soyipova emphasize fostering professional competence through dialogic learning, self-awareness, and creating a creative environment.

F. Karimova and M. Xakimova highlight the effectiveness of interactive methods, systemic thinking, and person-centered technologies in forming professional competence.

V. Allahverdiyeva recommends the IPM method for developing creative competence in multilingual contexts through personal portfolios for foreign students. E. Moydinova identifies linguistic, methodological, cultural, and ICT competencies as the foundation of professional competence. F. Rustamov emphasizes digital tools, intercultural communication, and continuous professional growth as critical factors.

E.N. Frantseva demonstrate that a communicative approach can prepare students for independent thinking, creativity, and intercultural communication. S.V. Tetina stresses that a teacher must be self-developing, open to innovation, reflective, and ready for intercultural communication.

Professional competence is the set of knowledge, skills, abilities, and aptitudes necessary to successfully perform a profession. It primarily serves to ensure professional success in the workplace and consists of the following core components:

1. *Knowledge* - theoretical knowledge related to the profession, methodology, regulations, and standards.
2. *Skills* - practical tools, techniques, and methods applied in performing the profession.
3. *Abilities* - the capacity to effectively apply knowledge and skills in various professional situations.
4. *Personal aptitudes* - creativity, teamwork, problem-solving, time management, and other personal qualities.

Professional competence must continuously evolve, as the modern labor market introduces new demands and changes. A high level of professional competence enables a worker or specialist to perform their duties effectively and with quality.

Creative competence is an individual's ability to generate new ideas, find innovative and effective solutions to problems, and apply existing knowledge and experience in novel ways. In other words, it is the individual's capacity to adopt a creative approach and independently develop their thinking. Creative competence may include the following components:

1. *Creative thinking* - the ability to generate new ideas, make unconventional decisions, and view situations from different perspectives.

2. *Innovation creation* - developing new methods and techniques, adapting to change, and implementing innovations.

3. *Problem-solving* - devising innovative approaches to complex situations beyond conventional solutions.

4. *Communication* - effectively sharing creative ideas, collaborating in groups, and implementing new ideas.

Creative competence is vital not only in arts or sciences but also in pedagogy and other professional fields. For instance, it is essential for teachers to apply new and effective approaches in teaching students.

The concept of *professional-creative competence* refers to a teacher's ability to apply creative approaches in pedagogical activities, enhance students' motivation to learn a language, and establish successful communication with them. The importance of creative approaches in developing a teacher's professional competence lies in enabling teachers to engage students with new ideas, apply interactive methods, and encourage independent thinking. The components forming professional-creative competence include and are described as follows:

1. *Linguistic Competence* - Mastery of the German language (vocabulary, grammar, phonetics, stylistics). Creative use of language tools: rephrasing, selecting synonyms, and adapting speech.

2. *Communicative Competence* - Oral and written communication skills in various situations. Ability to improvise and express emotions, opinions, and ideas through language.

3. *Methodological (Pedagogical) Competence* - Knowledge of modern methods of teaching German. Designing creative tasks such as role plays, debates, projects, and dramatizations.

4. *Information and Digital Competence* - Using digital technologies (online resources, multimedia, interactive platforms). Creating creative tasks using apps, videos, and podcasts.

5. *Cultural Competence* - Knowledge of the culture, literature, music, and traditions of German-speaking countries. Developing students' creative thinking by integrating cultural materials into lessons.

6. *Reflective and Research Competence* - Ability to analyze one's own teaching practice. Developing original methodologies and creatively interpreting one's experience.

7. *Social and Personal Competence* - Empathy, creativity, leadership qualities. Inspiring students and fostering their creative engagement.

This competence is particularly crucial for educators, researchers, and professionals in creative fields, as they must innovate and respond to evolving demands.

The competence of a foreign language teacher entails linguistic knowledge (mastery of the language), pedagogical skills (effective lesson delivery), the ability to apply methodological approaches, and being creative, responsible, and motivated.

DISCUSSION

The literature review and analyses indicate that independent work tasks and assignments for enhancing students' professional-creative competence have not been thoroughly explored as a distinct methodological approach in most sources. Hybrid (combined) methodologies for forming creative competence through independent work are absent. Specifically, in the context of foreign language teaching, no system of tasks and assignments has been developed to enhance professional and creative competence. Independent work lacks sufficient tasks that simulate real-life professional scenarios, intercultural situations, and activities fostering creative thinking.

Based on these findings, this dissertation aims to enhance the professional-creative competence of future foreign language teachers through an independent work tasks and assignments approach.

The purpose and relevance of the proposed methodology lie in treating independent work not merely as grammatical or translation exercises but as a tool for developing professional-creative competence. This approach comprehensively forms methodological, communicative, creative, and reflective competencies. By integrating digital resources such as Quizlet, Padlet, Canva, Genially, and ChatGPT, independent work is infused with a creative approach, enabling the creation of educational resources. This aligns with the communicative methodology of foreign language teaching. As a result, the novelty of this research lies in developing an experimental methodology for enhancing professional-creative competence through independent work. An integrative model of independent work tasks and assignments for enhancing the professional-creative competence of future foreign language teachers will be developed.

Based on this model, a methodological manual for independent work tasks and assignments to enhance the professional-creative competence of foreign language teachers will be developed. In the future, this manual can be used by higher education students, teachers, and secondary school teachers in educational processes.

CONCLUSION

The literature review demonstrates that forming the professional-creative competence of future foreign language teachers requires a comprehensive, integrated, and person-centered approach. This approach must harmonize methodological, communicative, creative, and technological components. Modern education has proven that creative competence can be formed using CLIL, TBL, PBL, IPM, creolized texts, digital platforms, reflection, and creative approaches. Additionally, adapting international experiences to the local context and using an independent work tasks model can serve as a crucial tool for modernizing pedagogical education.

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